

Automation of the training process for highly qualified athletes

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15320142>

Abstract

The work is devoted to the issues of automation of the process of training highly qualified athletes, as well as optimization of the construction of the training process based on the use of innovative technologies that contribute to increasing its efficiency with optimal expenditure of time and energy of athletes. The model is based on a database that includes the results of instrumental, laboratory and clinical studies and sports tests. The analysis of more than 100 medical, anthropometric indicators and results of sports tests at the beginning, in the process of preparation and before the competition. All detected deviations were corrected during the training of athletes for various competitions. As a result of the automation of the process, the development of overtraining syndrome was predicted (OS) and the reasons for its development have been eliminated. The research was carried out on the basis of the Uzbek State University of Physical Culture and Sports and the Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute.

Keywords: automation, training process, training apparatus.

Introduction

The problem of building sports training is one of the most difficult in sports. In the theory of sports, a formalistic concept has developed, which reduces the construction of training to the "construction" of its content from separate "building blocks". These are "sets" of microcycles or mesocycles of various types, which are composed into corresponding cycles of a larger scale. The training process is an extremely complex phenomenon. The last decade has been characterized by an unprecedented increase in sports achievements and their high density at a sub-record level, a

toughening of competitive struggle at major intercontinental competitions, a significant increase in the volume and intensity of loads, etc. All this requires a revision of the forms and principles of building sports training to optimize the training process.

Modern sport is characterized by the transience of technical and tactical actions that require the athlete to maximize muscular efforts in a time deficit. Optimization of the training process implies achieving the planned result with a minimum spending of time and energy. Specifically in relation to sports, this means the selection of effective means of training and their distribution within a particular stage (period, cycle) in order to achieve the required sports result with the amount of training work minimized to the possible limit. Thus, the volume of the load acts as the main criterion for optimizing the training process.

Currently, an increasing number of coaches in the preparation of highly qualified athletes expand the arsenal of physical exercises used, use complex types of training, allowing to achieve good sports form, while doing several kinds of sports (Loginov, 1999). This approach is especially common abroad. Also, many athletes, especially those who specialize in endurance sports, have repeatedly noticed that the positive effect of good sports form, achieved through training sessions in several sports, can manifest itself not only in improving general physical fitness, but also in better performance of motor actions. We regard the modern sports training control system as a process of directed influence on the athlete's neuromuscular apparatus, which ensures the optimal training effect. The complexity and versatility of the training process in complex trainings raises the problem of obtaining objective information, searching for new methods that allow the most complete realization of the athlete's motor capabilities, which is impossible without the use of modern technical means. Depending on the functions in the training process, these can be simulators or automated control systems (computer devices and technologies).

In the modern training process, an increasingly significant place is given to automation equipment equipped with computer technology. This is due to the complication of the training process control system itself, as well as the expansion of various practical tasks that can be solved using a computer and special applied programs. Nowadays, computers are mainly used to assess training loads, to study individual sides of readiness, to model the process of motor skills formation. The theory and practice of sports training put forward the tasks of developing new computer technologies - measuring and diagnostic equipment using microprocessors and automated training systems with artificial intelligence, working in the environment of experimental control systems.

The development of computer teaching aids, the methodology of their application directly in the training process is an important factor in ensuring optimal control of the training process for athletes specializing in various sports.

The methodological basis for the creation of decision-making algorithms in the management of sports training is the further development of the concept of "artificial control environment" (Ratov et al., 2007) and the development on this basis of methodological techniques for managing the training process based on the results of the analysis of individual components of readiness for use in information-expert systems, as well as the implementation structural control scheme: from predicting the expected result to managing the process of forming a rational movement, to managing the process of sports training. Biomechanical, physiological and power indicators of athletes' motor actions, which can lead to an increase in sports results, are discussed in detail in (Yermolayev et al., 1991).

The growth of sports achievements increasingly depends on the effectiveness of the system of long-term training of athletes, which can be defined as a rationally organized process of education, upbringing and training.

In various sports, where the result is determined not so much by absolute strength as by the speed of movements, the leading direction of training is the development of speed-strength qualities. At the present stage, it is this problem that is not given due attention in the training of high-class athletes.

Purpose of the study

The proposed system is based on the position of the fundamental possibility of forming a rhythmically-speed basis of a motor skill in specially created conditions, corresponding to the level of the planned achievement with the subsequent "filling" of this basis with "power" content. At the same time, attention is drawn to the fact that the athlete performs a specially designed modified version of the movement, the main parameters of which nevertheless meet the conditions necessary to achieve the planned record result.

Materials and methods

The following methods are used in the work:

- transformation of the types of features (Narzullaev et al., 2020);
- reducing the dimension of the original feature space (Zhuravljov et al., 2006; Nishanov et al., 2021; Kamilov et al., 2012);
- data mining (Fazilov et al., 2019; Fazilov, Mirzaev, Nurmukhamedov et al., 2019);
- automation and modeling;
- questionnaires of athletes and coaches;
- sports testing.

As the initial information, a table of experimental data was used, obtained by questioning of 2520 athletes (various types of wrestling). There were created a table of experimental data (TED), consisting of 2520 lines (the number of examined sportsmen) and 48 columns (the sportsmen's health risk factors described above) and is the basis of the database. Methods of data mining [8-9] were chosen as methods for assessing health risk factors for highly qualified sportsmen. In this case, all the signs (columns) of the TED must be quantitative (all mathematical operations are performed). The qualitative signs, there were applied methods of transforming the types of signs (Narzullaev et al., 2020), allowing by digitization to translate these signs into quantitative. To determine the most important risk factors that have the greatest impact on health sportsman, the methods of decreasing the dimensionality of the initial attribute space for describing objects described in (Zhuravljov et al., 2006; Nishanov et al., 2021; Kamilov et al., 2012) were applied. To solve the above problems, the intelligent data analysis system SITO-PC was used, developed by the authors of this article and implemented in an integrated development environment programmatically Delphi 10 Seattle software.

The work was carried out in accordance with a grant from the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan (project № BA-A5-005).

Results

In recent years, there has been a significant expansion of the competition calendar. Competitions are the basis of the specifics of sports, and therefore their role in the process of training an athlete is extremely high. It should be noted that with an increase in qualifications, the importance of competitions increases accordingly. During the competition, the requirements are imposed on the athlete that cause the maximum specific tension of the functional systems. Therefore, the need to improve the effectiveness of the training process of highly qualified athletes is beyond doubt, since the further increase in the level of technical and tactical skill is based on the high potential of the specific performance of the athlete. In this regard, the issues of building and automating sports training are the subject of interest of entire scientific teams and scientists of various scientific profiles, as well as experienced teacher-trainers.

Thus, the lack of scientifically grounded recommendations on the problem of optimizing the training process and increasing the efficiency of building training determines the relevance of this study, since the implementation of this project will contribute to improving the system of training athletes of members of national teams of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Olympic Games, World Championships, Asia and other responsible international tournaments.

The quantitative characteristics of muscle strength during muscle contraction without changing their length (static mode) and with changing length (dynamic mode) do not coincide.

Muscle tension developed in a muscle in a static mode approaches maximum strength in absolute terms. Such conditions are not suitable for changing the maximum dynamic force. But if the muscle is capable of shortening at maximum load, then the stress developed by it will be less than the maximum. Consequently, the absolute values of the dynamic force under the conditions that allow it to be measured will always be somewhat less than the maximum.

It is advisable to use a universal dynamographic stand (UDS) as instrumental research methods. The registration of the characteristics of the level of speed-power readiness is carried out using the UDS. The universal dynamographic stand allows registering the characteristics of athletes' efforts in isometric and explosive modes. It also allows you to determine the absolute, explosive, starting and accelerating forces of the leg extensor muscles.

Target planning of long-term sports training is of the utmost importance for effective management of the training process. Effective use of means and methods of comprehensive training, determination of the optimal ratio of the volumes of general and special training of athletes is of great importance for the successful implementation of a long-term training of an athlete. For an effective educational and training process, a rational system of using training and competitive loads in the process of long-term training is extremely important, this will be facilitated by the information obtained with the help of the UDS.

In the process of controlling the training process using the CDS, direct communication is information about what and how to do in order to achieve the set goal. Feedback is information obtained during the control of training by comparing the achieved indicators and the conditions for their implementation with the parameters of direct communication and model characteristics. Based on the comparison of direct and feedback indicators, decisions are made in the form of correction of training programs that regulate the further content and orientation of the competitive and training processes in various training cycles.

The issues of automation and modeling have been studied in various fields of science and production: in the automation of the activities of the farm of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Narzullaev et al., 2022); when modeling hydromechanical (Ilhamov et al., 2021) processes; in modeling in medicine (Nishanov et al., 2020) and sports (Davronbek Narzullaev et al., 2021; Umarov et al., 2019).

From the very beginning of training and until the planned result is achieved at the competition, the athlete implements the target motional task, a number of the main parameters of which do not change and constantly correspond to the levels necessary for performing a real exercise.

This approach is the basis, for example, of the "ACS-CT" system, a distinctive feature of which is the presence of means for modeling competitive activity, as close as possible to real

conditions and its adaptability, i.e. the ability to develop algorithms for improving sports and technical skills in the process of training (Loginov. 1999).

In our approach, the automated control system for the training process of highly qualified athletes includes an information system consisting of a database that identifies 48 risk factors for health and sports readiness of athletes, as well as special simulators for single combatants, which allow to optimize the construction of the training process on based on the use of innovative technologies that contribute to improving its efficiency with the optimal expenditure of time and energy of athletes.

Discussion

On the basis of the above methodological provisions with the purposeful use of the UDS, the optimal control of the process of long-term training of athletes will be carried out. Optimal training management is an effective system of scientifically grounded organization of the educational and training process. Such management is expressed in the creation of conditions conducive to the effective implementation of the objective laws of sports training. The training system is the most important part in the overall training system for athletes. The rapid growth of achievements in world sport urgently requires a tireless search for new, more and more effective means, methods and organizational forms of training athletes, which will be facilitated by the information obtained with the help of the UDS.

The striving for the highest achievements in the world arena does not stop, and their growth rates practically do not weaken. This is due to the use of the most effective means and methods of training, intensification of the training process and competitive activity, the use of a special nutrition system and optimization of the mode of life, rest and recovery, the use of high-class athletes in training will make a big role. The constant improvement of sports equipment and equipment, the conditions of the venues and the rules of the competition also contributes to the striving for the highest achievements. Achieving top-class results requires an athlete tremendous effort and time to prepare. UDS will reduce the time spent on the development of speed-strength abilities due to targeted diagnostics and the timely development of speed-strength indicators.

The basic model of the training system in a large adaptation cycle (BAC) is offered to the attention of specialists as one of the possible options for constructing training (Fig. 1). The large adaptation cycle is a fundamentally new form of training organization in sports, which provides for an organic connection and interdependence of competitive activity and the steady development of the adaptation process. The model includes as its main components:

- model of the dynamics of the "output" power of the body in a specific motor mode (W);

its gradual transfer to the level of quantitative programming with a significant reduction in time and energy of the athlete (Toychiev et al., 2022; Paiziev et al., 2017).

The automated system proposed by us solves the problem of controlling the process of sports training of athletes using a control personal computer. The system is made on the basis of computer technology, UDS, measuring and diagnostic equipment, operating under the control of the control program.

The system provides the necessary conditions for the fulfillment of motor tasks and assumes the function of bringing the controlled indicators to the planned quality characteristics. As part of the system, automated forms of express control over the activity of the students' functional systems are used, which act as a factor in the control of the training process and develop control techniques for optimizing the motor regime. The system uses a model that implements 4 links of one methodological chain of the training process with a specifically expressed target orientation: analysis; planning; control; control.

The main features of the system:

- modeling the optimal characteristics of movements to achieve the planned result;
- development of control action;
- analysis of the impact result;
- development of a new solution;
- a rational motor mode, implemented in the conditions of simulators with feedback, taking into account the individual capabilities of an athlete on the basis of psychophysical interfacing with a computer;
- express - assessment of the state of the body in the mode of distribution of time in the classroom;
- formation of a data bank for analysis;
- issue of recommendations.

Purpose:

- assessment of physical condition;
- control over the effectiveness of training;
- taking into account the fulfillment of motional tasks;
- optimization of motor modes.

The automated system proposed by us solves the problem of controlling the training process using a control computer. Based on the analysis of athletes' personal data with the use of methods for reducing the dimension of the attribute space of object description and intellectual analysis, this system determines the most important risk factors for an athlete's health and gives recommendations for eliminating these factors.

Conclusion

Automation of the process of training highly qualified athletes is the most important strategic task aimed at improving the system of sports training. Projects for the development of special software designed for automated collection, storage and analysis of integrated control data with the ability to control the training process of athletes; on the development of systems for automated modeling, design and forecasting of the state of the body of athletes, checking the adequacy of the developed model in a series of computational experiments for solving problems of control of the training process at various stages of long-term training and in the system of an annual training cycle are currently the most in demand in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The totality of computerized techniques allows for the automation of the system of integrated control and management of the training process of athletes.

• The proposed automated control system for the training process of athletes includes the following components:

- database of risk factors for the health status of athletes;
- a battery of tests to determine the functional and physical fitness of athletes;
- special simulators for determining the speed-strength qualities of combatants;
- model characteristics of an athlete by type of sport, contributing to the improvement of competitive activity;
- training program for highly qualified athletes.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest in the composition of this research.

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